

Xingxiangyou 77 is considered a semi-aromatic hybrid rice. It produces only partially aromatic grains on each plant (owing to F₂ segregation for aromatic genes). Consumers prefer semi-aromatic rice to pure aromatic rice.

Using the 1-9 scales of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, the hybrid scored 6 for leaf blast, 7 for neck blast, and 7 for bacterial leaf blight.

When planted as late rice in the double-cropping system in Hunan,

Xingxiangyou 77 matured in about 115 d (Table 1). It was about 98 cm tall with strong tillering ability. Its seed set was 75% with a mean of 105-110 spikelets panicle⁻¹ and a 1000-grain weight of 27-28 g. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

New rice varieties for the rainfed lowlands of Cambodia

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The rainfed lowland rice ecosystem is highly diverse in Cambodia. Several niches exist within the ecosystem, each of which may require different rice varieties of early, medium, or late maturity.

The Varietal Recommendations Committee (VRC) of the Cambodian Department of Agronomy approved the release of three modern, photo-period-insensitive, early-duration (less than 120 d) and three modern, photo-period-insensitive, medium-duration (120-150 d) varieties selected by CIAP between 1990 and 1993. In 1995, the VRC approved the release of six pureline selections from traditional Cambodian varieties for cultivation in the rainfed lowland ecosystem.

The six selections originated from the traditional varieties Pram Bei Kuor (PPD679), Sambak Kraham (PPD597), Sraem Choab Chan (Germplasm B-293), Changkom Ropeak (Germplasm 90B-528), Kantuy Touk (PPD156), and Sae Nang (Germplasm 90B-429). The VRC decided that all varieties released in Cambodia will be assigned continuous numbers following the letters CAR, which signify "Cambodia rice." So these selections were named CAR1-CAR6, respectively.

In the early 1970s, Cambodia's rice germplasm collections were sent to IRRI headquarters in the Philippines for safekeeping. Many of these varieties were subsequently lost in Cambodia

Table 1. Yield (t ha⁻¹) of photoperiod-sensitive, traditional medium- and late-duration rice varieties and checks^a for rainfed lowland ecosystem in Cambodia.

Year	Trial ^b	Medium-duration varieties				Late-duration varieties			
		CAR 1	CAR 2	CAR 3	MS	CAR 4	CAR 5	CAR 6	TS2
1990	PYT (0, 2)	-	-	-	-	4.2	3.3	3.9	3.4
1991	PYT (1, 3)	3.3	3.8	3.8	3.2	5.2	4.4	4.6	3.7
1992	AYT (9, 6)	3.0	3.3	3.3	2.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	3.9
1993	AYT (9, 8)	3.2	3.4	3.3	2.9	3.6	3.5	3.4	2.6
1994	AYT (6, 10)	3.0	3.1	3.3	2.6	3.7	3.4	3.6	2.8
	Mean	3.1	3.3	3.3	2.8	4.0	3.7	3.8	3.0
	% Increase over check	11	18	18	0	29	19	23	0

^aChecks for medium- and late-duration trials are Mahsuri (MS) and Toul Samrong 2 (TS2). ^bPYT = preliminary yield trial, AYT = advanced yield trial. The first and second values in parentheses refer to the number of locations involved in medium- and late-duration trials, respectively.

Table 2. Date of 50% flowering, growth duration, and plant height of photoperiod-sensitive, traditional medium- and late-duration varieties and checks. 1993-94 wet seasons. Cambodia.

Variety	Date of 50% flowering		Growth duration ^a (d)		Height ^a (cm) 1992-94
	1993	1994	1993	1994	
<i>Medium-duration</i>					
CAR1	4 Nov-3 Dec	13 Nov-1 Dec	160 (145-172)	166 (150-180)	127 (95-180)
CAR2	7 Nov-9 Dec	22 Oct-10 Dec	162 (146-178)	165 (150-182)	126 (90-178)
CAR3	1 Nov-3 Dec	7 Nov-26 Nov	156 (138-172)	162 (150-175)	122 (89-167)
MS	9 Oct-4 Dec	8 Oct-15 Nov	150 (128-170)	142 (135-151)	113 (81-156)
Sowing time	22 Jun-31 Jul	21 Jun-17 Jul	22 Jun-31 Jul	21 Jun-17 Jul	-
<i>Late-duration</i>					
CAR4	15 Nov-4 Dec	14 Nov-28 Nov	171 (162-182)	174 (160-186)	132 (93-161)
CAR5	17 Nov-10 Dec	16 Nov-1 Dec	173 (162-182)	177 (166-190)	134 (93-184)
CAR6	13 Nov-5 Dec	14 Nov-28 Nov	171 (161-183)	174 (161-187)	129 (94-183)
TS2	25 Nov-12 Dec	18 Nov-6 Dec	182 (171-195)	182 (169-196)	125 (96-194)
Sowing time	18 Jun-14 Jul	15 Jun-20 Jul	18 Jun-14 Jul	15 Jun-20 Jul	-

^aThe first value is the mean. Values in parentheses represent the range.

because of the lack of cold storage facilities and the civil unrest in the 1970s. In the 1980s, the collections were returned to Prey Phdau Station at the government's request. The source populations for CAR1, CAR2, and CAR5 belonged to these collections and could have been completely lost if they had not been conserved at IRRI's International Rice Genebank. The source populations for the other varieties released were part of the CIAP

germplasm collection obtained through the joint efforts of the Department of Agronomy, provincial agriculture offices, nongovernment organizations, and CIAP.

On the basis of preliminary yield trials (PYT) and advanced yield trials (AYT) conducted for several years at multiple locations, CAR1 yielded 11% more than the check Mahsuri while CAR2 and CAR3 yielded 18% more (Table 1). CAR4 has a yield advantage of

29%; CAR5, 19%, and CAR6, 23%, over check Toul Samrong 2.

The new varieties are photoperiod-sensitive. They can be sown between May and August and still flower at a given range of time. CAR1, CAR2, and CAR3 are medium-duration varieties. CAR1 and CAR3 can flower as early as the first week of November while CAR2 can flower as early as the third

week of October (Table 2). CAR4, CAR5, and CAR6 are late-duration varieties. They can flower as early as the second week of November. Their mean growth duration is about a week longer than that of CAR1, CAR2, and CAR3. In general, they are taller than the medium-duration varieties.

A sensory test using 94 evaluators showed that the raw and cooked rice

qualities of the six varieties were acceptable. The raw milled rice acceptability for CAR3 was 75%. It was at least 90% for the other varieties. Cooked rice acceptability was 87% for CAR1 and CAR2 and more than 95% for the other varieties. All six varieties have medium-sized grains, with length-breadth ratio ranging from 2.49 for CAR3 to 2.99 for CAR4 and CAR6. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

FARO 45 to FARO 49: two early-maturing and three medium-maturing upland rice varieties released in Nigeria

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Upland rice is grown on 30% of the 1.77 million ha planted to rice in Nigeria. In August 1996, the National Crop Variety Release Committee released two early-maturing and three medium-maturing

upland rice varieties for different agroecological zones in Nigeria. Their characteristics are shown in the table.

FARO 45 is more suited to the northwestern and northeastern zones, while FARO 46 is recommended for all the five agroecological zones of the country. Both are harvested at around 100 d after seeding.

FARO 47 is recommended for the southeastern zone, and FARO 48 and FARO 49 are suitable for hydromorphic areas of the Niger, Benue, and Plateau states in central Nigeria and upland areas of southwestern Nigeria. These three varieties have durations of 115-120 d.

All varieties are ITA lines selected from the crosses made in IITA, Ibadan. FARO 45 is ITA 257 line, selected in F₄ generation from a three-way cross made in 1979. It involved parents such as IRAT 13, Dourado Precoce, LAC 23, IET1444, OS 6, CP-SLO, and TN1. FARO 46 is ITA 150 line, selected in F₅ from a single cross made in 1976. It involved parents such as 63-83, ROK 1, SE363G, and Dourado Precoce. FARO 47 is ITA 117 line, selected in F₅ from a cross made in 1975. It involved parents such as 13A, CP-SLO, TN1, and OS 6. FARO 48 is ITA301 line, selected in F₈ from a three-way cross among IRAT13, Dourado Precoce, and Padipayak

Agronomic characteristics of two early- and three medium-maturing upland rice varieties. Ibadan, Nigeria.

	FARO 45	FARO 46	FARO 47	FARO 48	FARO 49
Designation	ITA257	ITA150	ITA117	ITA301	ITA315
Line	TOX10114-1	TOX502-41-1-1	TOX356-1-1-1	TOX854-101-3-201-1-1-1	TOX936-397-9-1-2
Cross	IRAT13/Dourado Precoce/TOX490-1	63-83/Multiple parent#23 ^b	13A218-3-1-3/ 1529-430-3/ TOX7-4-2-5-2	IRAT13/Dourado Precoce// Padipayak	IR1529-430-3/ Iguape Cateto
Year of hybridization	1979	1975	1975	1978	1979
Plant height (cm)	100	110	105	100	100
Days to 50% flowering	70	75	85	98	90
Blast resistance ^a	1	1	1	1	1
Drought tolerance ^a	1	1	3	1	1
Leaf scald ^a	3	1	1	5	7
Brown rice length (mm)	6.5	7.5	7.2	7.4	7.0
Brown rice width (mm)	2.9	2.6	2.2	2.4	2.7
Brown rice L/W	2.2	2.9	3.1	3.1	2.6
Brown rice shape	Medium bold	Long bold	Long slender	Long slender	Long bold
Chalkiness ^a	1	1	1	5	9
Gelatinization temperature ^a	3	5	5	5	3
Gel consistency ^a	3	5	5	5	1
Amylose(%)	17.4	22.5	19.5	16.4	16.2
Husk color	Golden	Golden	Straw	Straw	Straw
1000 grain weight (g)	31.0	33.5	26.5	29.5	30.5
Av grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2.0	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.0
Yield potential (t ha ⁻¹)	3.5	3.0	3.5	3.5	3.5

^aSES scale (IRRI 1996). ^bMultiple parent #23: ROK1, SE 363G, and Dourado Precoce.